

Tabela de artigos selecionados

1

ID	Título	Ano
E01	A Relational Model for Playful and Smart Game Design [de Albuquerque et al. 2016]	2016
E02	Identifying and classifying learning entities for designing location-based serious games [Anastasiadou e Lameris 2016]	2016
E03	Pervasive games: giving a meaning based on the player experience [Arango-López et al. 2017]	2017
E04	What is going on with ubicomp games [Buzeto et al. 2012]	2012
E05	How Boardgame Players Imagine Interacting With Technology [Farkas et al. 2024]	2024
E06	Towards a Taxonomy of AI in Hybrid Board Games [Gómez-Maureira et al. 2020]	2020
E07	Towards Pervasive Augmented Reality: Context-Awareness in Augmented Reality [Grubert et al. 2016]	2016
E08	Ontology-Based Domain Analysis for Model Driven Pervasive Game Development [Guo et al. 2018]	2018
E09	PerGO: An Ontology towards Model Driven Pervasive Game Development [Guo et al. 2014]	2014
E10	Classifying Pervasive Games: On Pervasive Computing and Mixed Reality [Hinske et al. 2007]	2007
E11	Classifying Multiplayer Hybrid Games to Identify Diverse Player Participation [Javanshir et al. 2019]	2019
E12	Games as Blends: Understanding Hybrid Games [Kankainen et al. 2017]	2017
E13	Hybrid Board Game Design Guidelines [Kankainen e Paavilainen 2019]	2019
E14	Understanding smart device tabletop games [Kankainen e Tyni 2014]	2014
E15	Two Worlds, One Gameplay: A Classification of Visual AR Games [Knauer e Mütterlein 2016]	2016
E16	Digital–Physical Reality Game: Mapping of Physical Space With Fantasy in Context-Based Learning Games [Kwon et al. 2016]	2016
E17	Game space design foundations for trans-reality games [Lindley 2005]	2005
E18	Towards a new hybrid game model: designing tangible experiences [Oliveira et al. 2020]	2020
E19	“I love all the bits”: The Materiality of Boardgames [Rogerson et al. 2016]	2016

1

ID	Título	Ano
E20	More Than a Gimmick - Digital Tools for Boardgame Play [Rogerson et al. 2021]	2021
E21	Unpacking “Boardgames with Apps”: The Hybrid Digital Boardgame Model [J. Rogerson et al. 2021]	2021
E22	Design of technology-based pervasive gaming experiences: properties and degrees of pervasiveness [Salazar et al. 2022]	2022
E23	Geogames: A Conceptual Framework and Tool for the Design of Location-Based Games from Classic Board Games [Schlieder et al. 2005]	2005
E24	Dimensions of Hybrid in Playful Products [Tyni et al. 2013]	2013
E25	A method to assess pervasive qualities in mobile games [Valente et al. 2018]	2017
E26	Features and Checklists to Assist in Pervasive Mobile Game Development [Valente et al. 2013]	2013

Referências

- Anastasiadou, D. e Lameris, P. (2016). Identifying and classifying learning entities for designing location-based serious games. In *2016 11th International Workshop on Semantic and Social Media Adaptation and Personalization (SMAP)*, pages 133–138. IEEE.
- Arango-López, J., Gallardo, J., Gutiérrez, F. L., Cerezo, E., Amengual, E., e Valera, R. (2017). Pervasive games: giving a meaning based on the player experience. In *Proceedings of the XVIII international conference on human computer interaction*, pages 1–4.
- Buzeto, F., Castillo, A., Castanho, C. D., e Jacobi, R. P. (2012). What is going on with ubicomp games. In *XI Brazilian Symposium on Computer Games and Digital Entertainment-SBGAMES*, pages 1–7.
- de Albuquerque, A. P., Breyer, F. B., e Kelner, J. (2016). A relational model for playful and smart game design. In *International Conference of Design, User Experience, and Usability*, pages 252–263. Springer.
- Farkas, T., Hughes, N. G. J., e Fiebrink, R. (2024). How boardgame players imagine interacting with technology. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 8(CHI PLAY):1–24.
- Gómez-Maureira, M. A., Barbero, G., Freese, M., e Preuss, M. (2020). Towards a taxonomy of ai in hybrid board games. In *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on the Foundations of Digital Games*, pages 1–6.
- Grubert, J., Langlotz, T., Zollmann, S., e Regenbrecht, H. (2016). Towards pervasive augmented reality: Context-awareness in augmented reality. *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics*, 23(6):1706–1724.
- Guo, H., Gao, S., Trættemberg, H., Wang, A. I., e Jaccheri, L. (2018). Ontology-based domain analysis for model driven pervasive game development. *Information*, 9(5):109.

- Guo, H., Trættemberg, H., Wang, A. I., e Gao, S. (2014). Pergo: an ontology towards model driven pervasive game development. In *OTM Confederated International Conferences "On the Move to Meaningful Internet Systems"*, pages 651–654. Springer.
- Hinske, S., Lampe, M., Magerkurth, C., e Röcker, C. (2007). Classifying pervasive games: on pervasive computing and mixed reality. *Concepts and technologies for pervasive games-a reader for pervasive gaming research*, 1(20):1–20.
- J. Rogerson, M., A. Sparrow, L., e R. Gibbs, M. (2021). Unpacking “boardgames with apps”: The hybrid digital boardgame model. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pages 1–17.
- Javanshir, R., Carroll, B., e Millard, D. (2019). Classifying multiplayer hybrid games to identify diverse player participation. In *International Conference on Videogame Sciences and Arts*, pages 248–260. Springer.
- Kankainen, V., Arjoranta, J., e Nummenmaa, T. (2017). Games as blends: Understanding hybrid games. *Journal of Virtual Reality and Broadcasting*, (4).
- Kankainen, V. e Paavilainen, J. (2019). Hybrid board game design guidelines. In *Proceedings of DiGRA 2019 Conference: Game, Play and the Emerging Ludo-Mix*.
- Kankainen, V. e Tyni, H. (2014). Understanding smart device tabletop games. In *Proceedings of the 18th International Academic MindTrek Conference: Media Business, Management, Content & Services*, pages 238–241.
- Knauer, M. e Mütterlein, J. (2016). Two worlds, one gameplay: A classification of visual ar games. In *Proceedings of DiGRA/FDG 2016 Conference*.
- Kwon, C., Kim, Y., e Woo, T. (2016). Digital–physical reality game: Mapping of physical space with fantasy in context-based learning games. *Games and Culture*, 11(4):390–421.
- Lindley, C. A. (2005). Game space design foundations for trans-reality games: Keynote paper. *Advances in Computer Entertainment (ACE): Special Track on Game Development*.
- Oliveira, A. P., Sousa, M., Vairinhos, M., e Zagalo, N. (2020). Towards a new hybrid game model: designing tangible experiences. In *2020 IEEE 8th International Conference on Serious Games and Applications for Health (SeGAH)*, pages 1–6. IEEE.
- Rogerson, M. J., Gibbs, M., e Smith, W. (2016). "i love all the bits"the materiality of boardgames. In *Proceedings of the 2016 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*, pages 3956–3969.
- Rogerson, M. J., Sparrow, L. A., e Gibbs, M. R. (2021). More than a gimmick-digital tools for boardgame play. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 5(CHI PLAY):1–23.
- Salazar, J., López, J., Gutiérrez, F., e Trillo, J. (2022). Design of technology-based pervasive gaming experiences: properties and degrees of pervasiveness. In *Proceedings of the I Congreso Español de Videojuegos, Madrid, Spain*, pages 1–2.

- Schlieder, C., Kiefer, P., e Matyas, S. (2005). Geogames: A conceptual framework and tool for the design of location-based games from classic board games. In *International Conference on Intelligent Technologies for Interactive Entertainment*, pages 164–173. Springer.
- Tyni, H., Kultima, A., e Mäyrä, F. (2013). Dimensions of hybrid in playful products. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Making Sense of Converging Media*, pages 237–244.
- Valente, L., Feijó, B., e Leite, J. C. (2013). Features and checklists to assist in pervasive mobile game development. *Proceedings of SBGames 2013*, pages 90–99.
- Valente, L., Feijó, B., Leite, J. C. S. d. P., e Clua, E. (2018). A method to assess pervasive qualities in mobile games. *Personal and Ubiquitous Computing*, 22(4):647–670.